

A Study on Maneuverability of a Ship Equipped with the CFRP Propeller by Means of Simulation Model Including Engine Dynamics

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Abstract. A propeller made of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) is considered one of promising propulsion devices for energy saving. The CFRP propeller passively deforms its blade angle due to hydrodynamic loads. Since the deformation degree of the propeller blade is larger in regions where the propeller torque is essentially high, the propeller open-water characteristics of the CFRP propeller exhibit a lower gradient compared to those of a conventional metallic propeller, such as one made of nickel aluminum bronze. Therefore, a main engine with the CFRP propeller can be operated at a higher rotational speed compared with the conventional metallic propeller. Because the CFRP propeller needs a higher rotational speed to obtain the required propeller thrust, operating the main engine at higher rotational speeds can offer certain advantages. For example, the higher rotational speed can sometimes lead to more efficient fuel combustion performance. Here, though we have a lot of research on the propulsion performance of the CFRP propeller, there is almost no research on maneuverability of the ship equipping the CFRP propeller. In this study, authors investigated the maneuverability performance of the CFRP propeller through the numerical simulation of the turning test and the zigzag test. These results are compared with those obtained using a conventional metallic propeller. Formulations of the simulation model for predicting ship maneuvering motion are based on the MMG-type. Additionally, a notable feature of this simulation model is the explicit incorporation of diesel engine dynamics, including the fuel combustion process. The assessment reveals notable qualitative differences in the steady turning performance between the two propellers, primarily attributed to the engine characteristics.

Keywords: *Ship's maneuverability, CFRP propeller, MMG model, Engine dynamics.*

1. Introduction

Reducing GHG emissions from ships is important and long-term task, considering the set goal “zero GHG emission” in IMO/MEPC 80. On the other hand, since ship’s propulsion performance and maneuverability are in a kind of trade-off relation, sufficient performance for safety navigation should be kept, as investigated in discussions on the guideline for determining minimum propulsion power to maintain the ship’s maneuverability.

In this study, the Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) propeller [1], regarded as one of promising devices to improve the ship’s propulsion performance, is the focus. The CFRP propeller is lighter than a conventional metallic propeller, made of nickel aluminum bronze, and actively deforms its blade angle due to hydrodynamic loads in propeller rotation. Since the deformation amount of the propeller blade is larger where propeller torque is high, propeller open-water characteristics of the CFRP propeller exhibit a lower gradient than the characteristics of the conventional metallic propeller. Then, the CFRP propeller basically needs higher rotational speed than that of the conventional propeller to generate required propeller thrust. Therefore, a main engine with the CFRP propeller can be operated at higher rotational speed at the same ship velocity. Operating the main engine at higher rotational speed provides certain benefits. For example, the higher rotational speed of the main diesel engine can sometimes lead to more efficient fuel combustion performance, and degrees of freedom in ship design become higher. Merits of the CFRP propeller in the ship hydrodynamic propulsion performance were also found [2]. Results of sea trial of one 499GT chemical tanker show 9% improvement of shaft power to the conventional metallic propeller at its design speed, and reduced vibrations were also confirmed. The authors have also studied the propulsion performance in waves of a ship equipped with the CFRP propeller [3]. The purpose of that study was to assess the energy saving effects resulting from reduced load fluctuation in waves, under the assumption that reduced propeller torque fluctuations would lead to more stable fuel combustion and more efficient power generation. Through simulation-based assessment using hydrodynamic model for propeller torque in waves and engine model that explicitly accounts for the fuel combustion process, qualitative energy saving effects of the

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CFRP propeller were confirmed. On the other hand, despite several studies on the propulsion performance of the CFRP propeller, research on the maneuverability of ships equipped with CFRP propellers remains extremely limited.

In this study, the authors investigated the maneuverability performance of a ship equipped with the CFRP propeller through numerical simulation, including comparisons with the results when using the conventional metallic propeller. Maneuverability was evaluated based on the results of the turning test and the zigzag test. The simulation model for predicting ship's maneuvering motion is based on the MMG model [4], in which external forces and moment in the motion equations are formulated in a modular-type. Furthermore, model of the engine dynamics is coupled with the maneuvering model to explicitly analyze the influence of propeller material and its comprehensive effects on engine behavior, which is considered significant. The assessment also considers the impact of including or excluding the engine model. The simulation models are explained in detail in the section 2. The subject ship is a Panamax-size bulk carrier, and the construction of simulation models, including the design and modeling of the CFRP propeller, is described in the section 3. The section 4 discusses the maneuverability characteristics of the ship equipped with the CFRP propeller, focusing on maneuverability indices of the turning test and the zigzag test as well as steady turning performance.

2. Simulation models

This section explains the simulation models used to predict the ship's maneuvering motion. The study focuses on a ship equipped with a single propeller and single rudder system. The planar motion of the ship, induced by the propeller and the rudder is modeled using the standard MMG-type formulation [4]. External disturbances such as waves and winds are not considered, and thus the assessed results correspond to calm sea conditions. The model for predicting engine states (hereafter, engine model) includes equation of motion for shaft rotation, a governor model and an engine torque generation model. For the engine torque generation, the Combined CMV (C-CMV) model is adopted. Details of each model are presented in the following subsections.

2.1. Maneuvering motions

A coordinate system and motion equations for surge, sway and yaw direction are respectively shown in Figure 1 and Eq. (1). Figure 1 shows the relation of the earth fixed axes system ($o - xy$) and the body fixed axes system (mid-ship - XY).

Figure 1. A body fixed coordinate system for ship's planar motion.

$$\begin{cases} (m + m_x)\dot{u} - mv_m r - x_G m r^2 = -R_T + X_H + X_P + X_R \\ (m + m_y)v'_m + mur + x_G m \dot{r} = Y_H + Y_R \\ (I_{zG} + mx_G^2 + J_z)\dot{r} + x_G m(v'_m + ur) = N_H + N_R \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where m denotes the mass [kg], m_x : the added mass for surge mode [kg], x_G : the longitudinal position of ship's center of gravity [m], m_y : the added mass for sway direction [kg], I_{zG} : the inertia moment for yaw direction [kgm²], J_z : the added inertia moment [kgm²]. The R_T denotes the ship hull resistance in calm water, and the index H, P, and R respectively shows component of Hull, Propeller and Rudder in the external force or moment.

The R_T model is shown in Eq. (2).

$$\begin{cases} R_T = \frac{1}{2} \rho S_W u^2 C_T \\ C_T = (1 + k)C_{F0} + C_W[F_n] + \Delta C_F \\ C_{F0} = \frac{0.075}{(\log_{10}[R_n] - 2)^2} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where ρ denotes the fluid density [kg/m³], S_W : the wet surface area of the hull [m²], k : the form factor, F_n : the Froude number, R_n : the Reynolds number. The C_T is the total resistance coefficient, consisting of the viscous resistance coefficient ($(1 + k)C_{F0}$, ΔC_F) and the wave making resistance coefficient C_W . The C_{F0} is the frictional resistance coefficient of the corresponding flat plate, whose formulation is introduced from ITTC 1957 recommended formula [5].

The hull force (X_H , Y_H) and the moment (N_H) induced by the ship's maneuvering motion are shown in Eq. (3).

$$\begin{cases} X_H = \frac{1}{2} \rho L d U^2 \{X_{vv} v'_m{}^2 + (X_{vr} + m'_y) v'_m r' + X_{rr} r'^2 + X_{vvv} v'_m{}^4 r'\} \\ Y_H = \frac{1}{2} \rho L d U^2 \{Y_v v'_m + (Y_r - m'_x) r' + Y_{vvv} v'_m{}^3 + Y_{vvr} v'_m{}^2 r' + Y_{vrr} v'_m r'^2 + Y_{rrr} r'^3\} \\ N_H = \frac{1}{2} \rho L^2 d U^2 \{N_v v'_m + N_r r' + N_{vvv} v'_m{}^3 + N_{vvr} v'_m{}^2 r' + N_{vrr} v'_m r'^2 + N_{rrr} r'^3\} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where L denotes the ship length between perpendiculars [m], d : the draft [m]. The apostrophe ($'$) of the motion variable u , v_m and r shows in the non-dimensional form, respectively calculated as $u' = u/U$, $v'_m = v_m/U$, $r' = r/(U/L)$. The coefficients on the motion variables in nondimensional form are the hydrodynamic derivatives.

In Eq. (3), the added mass in nondimensional form m'_y and m'_x are included in the formulations. This is because the determined value from results of the captive model test, as described in the following section, explicitly includes this component. Therefore, though the corresponding terms are appeared in lefthand side of the motion equation in some papers, as shown in Eq. (1), these terms are excluded in this study.

The propeller effective force (X_P) is shown in Eq. (4)

$$\begin{cases} X_P = (1 - t_p) \rho n_p^2 D^4 K_T [J] \\ K_T = c_{T0} + c_{T1} J + c_{T2} J^2 \\ J = \frac{u(1 - w_P)}{n_p D} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where t_p denotes the propeller thrust deduction ratio, n_p : the propeller rotational speed [1/s], D : the propeller diameter [m]. The K_T denotes the propeller thrust constant, given as a function of the propeller advance constant J , whose coefficients (c_{Ti}) are set from the propeller open-water characteristics (POC).

The propeller effective wake fraction (w_P) is given as Eq. (5), introducing the influence function f with the variable v_P which represents the geometrical inflow velocity at the propeller position in transverse direction.

$$\begin{cases} 1 - w_P = f(v'_P) \cdot (1 - w_{P0}) \\ v'_P = -(v'_m + x'_P r') \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where w_{P0} denotes the propeller effective wake fraction in straightly advance situation, x_P : the longitudinal propeller position [m].

The force (X_R , Y_R) and moment (N_R) induced by the rudder, and the rudder normal force (F_N) are respectively shown in Eqs. (6) and (7).

$$\begin{cases} X_R = -(1 - t_R)F_N \sin \delta \\ Y_R = -(1 + a_H)F_N \cos \delta \\ N_R = -(x_R + a_H x_H)F_N \cos \delta \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{cases} F_N = \frac{1}{2}\rho A_R(u_R^2 + v_R^2) \cdot C_{N0} \sin \alpha_R \\ \alpha_R = \delta - \delta_0 - \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{v_R}{u_R}\right) \\ u_R = u(1 - w_R) \sqrt{\eta \left\{ 1 + \frac{k_x}{\varepsilon} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{8K_T}{\pi J^2}} - 1 \right) \right\}^2} + 1 - \eta \\ v_R = -\gamma_R v - l_R r \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where A_R denotes the rudder area of side face [m²], C_{N0} : the gradient coefficient of the rudder normal force, δ_0 : the virtual zero rudder angle, w_R : the effective wake fraction at the rudder position, η : the ratio of the rudder area meeting the propeller slipstream to the rudder area A_R , k_x : the increment ratio of propeller slipstream, ε : the effective wake ratio shown as $(1 - w_R)/(1 - w_P)$.

The interaction coefficient between the hull and the rudder (t_R , a_H , x_H) can be given as a function of a variable which represents the propeller loading condition. Those trends are introduced in the following section with experimental results of the subject ship. It is known that values of the flow straightening coefficient (γ_R , l_R) are different to transverse inflow direction at rudder position [4]. The determined values for the subject ship shall be different according to the inflow directions, as shown in the following section.

2.2. Dynamics of a marine diesel engine

Incorporating engine dynamics into the prediction of the ship's maneuvering motion offers several advantages. The first merit is that the propeller rotational speed can vary according to loading condition of the main engine during maneuvers. This loading condition can be evaluated through the propeller torque. Therefore, a model of the propeller torque should account for the changes in propeller rotational speed as well as the hydrodynamic effects induced by the ship's maneuvering motion. In conventional maneuvering simulations, the propeller speed is usually fixed; by contrast, the proposed approach enables evaluation of the influences of transient changes in propeller speed on maneuvering behavior.

The second merit is the ability to evaluate engine states during maneuvering. Actually, there are few studies on ship's maneuverability coupling with the engine dynamics. In many cases, engine characteristics are treated as equilibrium conditions, such as in the IMO guideline on the minimum propulsion power for safe navigation. One notable exception is the study by M. Z. Aung et al [6], which addressed the prediction of the ship's minimum propulsion power under adverse weather conditions using the dynamics of the main diesel engine.

The equation of motion for the shaft rotation interfaces the hydrodynamic model with the engine dynamics and is given in Eq. (8). This model represents the response of the engine rotational speed based on the difference between the engine torque (Q_e) and the propeller load torque (Q_p).

$$2\pi(I_e + I_m + I_p + I_{p.add}) \frac{dn_e}{dt} = Q_e - Q_p \quad (8)$$

where I_e denotes the inertia moment of the main engine [kgm²], I_m : the inertia moment of the medium shaft [kgm²], I_p : the inertia moment of the propeller [kgm²], $I_{p.add}$: the added inertia moment of the propeller [kgm²].

The propeller torque model is shown in Eq. (9), using the torque constant (K_Q) provided by the POC, along with the propeller advance constant, consistent with the propeller thrust formulation shown in Eq. (4).

$$\begin{cases} Q_p = \rho n_p^2 D^5 K_Q J / \eta_R \\ K_Q = c_{Q0} + c_{Q1} J + c_{Q2} J^2 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where η_R denotes the ratio of propeller efficiency, c_{Qi} : the coefficients set from the POC.

In the field of propulsion system simulation, a cycle-mean value (CMV) engine modelling approach is widely used for evaluating both steady-state and transient responses. In the CMV approach [7], the engine is considered as a series of control volumes connected through flow restrictions, where air and exhaust gas flow continuously, disregarding the intermittent nature of the engine cylinder processes. Thus, the engine state variables during one rotation are treated as mean values over the full engine cycle, averaged across all cylinders. Combustion-related parameters can also be estimated within the CMV framework [8], introducing a phenomenological model for representing the closed part of the engine combustion cycle. Thus, the Combined-CMV approach is suitable for evaluating the fuel combustion process alongside other engine state variables in a cycle-averaged manner.

In this study, the Combined CMV (C-CMV) model is adopted to simulate engine torque and other engine states. The engine torque model is represented in Eq. (10) and consists of the indicated torque (Q_i) and the frictional torque (Q_{fr}). The indicated torque is the result of the combustion cycle simulation, represented by the indicated work per cylinder (W_i). Last but not least, the indicated work per cylinder is modified by a coefficient (η_c) which accounts for losses due to incomplete fuel combustion. This adjustment is essential, as the combustion process is highly sensitive to variations in the air-to-fuel ratio (λ_{af}). Under transient conditions – such as during engine response to propeller torque fluctuations – the optimal λ_{af} cannot be maintained, leading to degradation in engine performance [9].

For calculating the frictional torque, the Chen and Flynn [10] friction correlation is adopted, which expresses friction as a function of the maximum pressure in cylinder (P_Z) and the rotational speed (n_e). A scaling factor is applied to ensure that the frictional losses align with the available data.

$$\begin{cases} Q_e = Q_i - Q_{fr} \\ Q_i = \frac{z_c}{2\pi} W_i(\eta_c) \\ Q_{fr} = \frac{z_c V_c}{2\pi} [\alpha_f + \beta_f P_Z + \gamma_f n_e] \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where z_c denotes the cylinder number, V_c : the volume of one cylinder [m^3], ($\alpha_f, \beta_f, \gamma_f$): the scaling coefficients in the frictional torque model ([kg/ms^2], [$1/m^2$] and [kg/ms]).

The combustion cycle and thus the indicated work calculation require averaged values of the engine states, such as pressure, temperature and mass flows. The fundamental equations governing the temporal evolution of these state variables are derived from the first principles of mass and energy conservation laws along with the ideal gas law and equation of flow through an orifice. A detailed description of these equations is beyond the scope of this paper; readers interested in further technical details are referred to the following sources [7], [8], [9], [10].

The governor model is given as follows. This model represents the response of a mechanical type governor, consisted of the power piston model in Eq. (11), the deadband model in Eq. (12), the summation unit model in Eq. (13), the sensor model which reproduce measuring error between the set rotational speed (n_{sp}) and the engine speed (n_e) in Eq. (14) and the feedback function model in Eq. (15).

$$T_{pp} \frac{d\bar{h}_{p0}}{dt} = K_{SU} \bar{Z}_0 \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{Z}_0 = \begin{cases} \bar{\psi}_g - \varepsilon_{D.B}/2, & \text{if } \bar{\psi}_g > \varepsilon_{D.B}/2 \\ 0, & \text{if } |\bar{\psi}_g| \leq \varepsilon_{D.B}/2 \\ \bar{\psi}_g + \varepsilon_{D.B}/2, & \text{if } \bar{\psi}_g < -\varepsilon_{D.B}/2 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\psi}_g = \bar{Z}_S - \bar{Z}_{ip} - \bar{Z}_{f.b} + \bar{Z}_{AW} \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{Z}_S = K_S (\bar{n}_{sp} - \bar{n}_e) \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{cases} \bar{Z}_{f.b} = K_{f.b} \bar{h}_{p0} \\ T_i \frac{d\bar{Z}_{ip}}{dt} + \bar{Z}_{ip} = K_i T_i \frac{d\bar{h}_{p0}}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where T_{pp} [s] and K_{SU} denote the time constant and the gain of the power piston, $\varepsilon_{D.B.}$: the deadband width, K_S : the gain of the sensor, K_{fb} : the gain of the proportional feedback function, T_i [s] and K_i : the time constant and the gain of the isodromic feedback function. The overbar on a variable or a coefficient represents in the nondimensional form, basically normalized by its value in Maximum Continuous Rating (MCR) condition.

The governor model outputs the fuel pump rack amount (h_{p0}) toward the engine torque generation. The torque limiter function, which is one of safety devices of the diesel engine to prevent excess combustion in cylinder room, saturates the fuel pump rack amount from the governor function when that amount is larger than set limit value ($h_{p(Lim)}$). The torque limiter function model reproduces this saturation and outputs the fuel pump rack amount input in the engine torque generation model (h_p), as shown in Eq. (16). The limit value characteristic is shown in the section 3.

$$\overline{h_p} = \begin{cases} \overline{h_{p0}}, & \text{if } \overline{h_{p(Lim)}} \geq \overline{h_{p0}} \\ \overline{h_{p(Lim)}}, & \text{if } \overline{h_{p(Lim)}} < \overline{h_{p0}} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Here, the Z_{AW} in the summation unit model represents a feedback component from an anti wind-up function as shown in Eq. (17).

$$\overline{Z_{AW}} = K_{AW}(\overline{h_p} - \overline{h_{p0}}) \quad (17)$$

where K_{AW} denotes the gain of the anti wind-up function.

3. A subject ship and calculation conditions

3.1. The subject ship and its hydrodynamic characteristics

A subject ship is one Panamax-size bulk carrier, which was designed by National Maritime Research Institute and a full-scale ship is not constructed. The designed service speed in full loading condition is 14.5 kt (7.459 m/s) at engine output of 90% MCR. Principal parameters and the constants in the motion equation in Eq. (1) are respectively shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Principal parameters of the subject ship (Panamax-size bulk carrier).

L [m]	Breadth [m]	d [m]	Block Coefficient (C_B)	S_W [m ²]	x_P^* [m]	A_R [m ²]	x_R^* [m]
217.0	32.26	12.20	0.840	10999.7	-112.1	38.99	-115.7

*: the origin point is the center of gravity.

Table 2. The constants in the motion equation of the subject ship.

m [kg]	m_x / m	m_y / m	I_{zG} [kgm ²]	J_z [kgm ²]	x_G [m]
7.353E+7	0.06146	0.7996	2.164E+11	1.518E+11	7.214

One of subject propellers is the CFRP propeller which is designed authors' preceding study [3], in the framework of the corroborative research project by Nakashima Propeller Co. Ltd. and National Maritime Research Institute. In this project, the purpose was assessment of the fuel consumption performance in actual sea of the ship equipping the CFRP propeller, mainly focused on the effects of the reduced load fluctuations. Design policies of the subject propellers were fixed for comparing the performance by the CFRP propeller with by the conventional metallic propeller. Concretely as follows, (A) diameter and boss ratio of both propellers shall be same to the originally designed propeller whose wing section is MAU, (B) the thrust constant and the torque constant of both propeller at the standard point ($J=0.6$) in the service speed shall be equal, (C) wing section of the metallic propeller shall be same to the deformed CFRP propeller where propels at the standard condition as in (B), (D) difference between the maximum torque constant of the CFRP propeller and its minimum value in the J range from 0.3 to 0.9 shall be 20% reduced than that of the metallic propeller. Based on these policies, the CFRP propeller and the metallic propeller were designed for the same subject ship, using the CFD software SC/Tetra [11] for computation of hydrodynamic force and elastic deformation, as in the work by Hasuike et al [12]. Principal parameters of the subject propellers are shown in Table 3. The inertia moment of both propellers is calculated by their material and

blade shape. The added inertia moment of the metallic propeller is set as 25% value of the mass inertia moment, based on an empirical rule. The added inertia moment of the CFRP propeller shall be set equaled to of the metallic propeller, since projected area of the rotating propeller in transverse direction can be regarded as almost same.

The POC of the subject two propellers are shown in Figure 2. The points show computed results by the SC/Tetra, and the lines show second-order fitted curves by the computed point, corresponded to the formulations shown in Eqs. (4) and (16). The set coefficients for the POC of both propellers are given in Table 4.

Table 3. Principal parameters of the subject propellers (“CFRP” and “Metal”).

Item	Diameter [m]	Boss ratio	Blade number	I_p [kgm ²]	$I_{p.add}$ [kgm ²]
CFRP	7.1	0.180	4	7540	6765
Metal				27060	

Figure 2. Propeller open-water characteristics of the subject two propellers.

Table 4. Coefficients of the fitted curve of the thrust constant and the torque constant of the subject propellers.

	c_{T0}	c_{T1}	c_{T2}	c_{Q0}	c_{Q1}	c_{Q2}
CFRP	0.3852	-0.3452	-0.06711	0.03718	-0.006378	-0.03203
Metal	0.4399	-0.4929	0.0250	0.04578	-0.03484	-0.01386

The constants or the coefficients in the models for simulating the ship’s maneuvering motion, given in the subsection 2.1, are basically determined from the results by the scale-model test. The scale of a ship model is 1/47.3, and the length of the model is 4.585m. A propeller model for the ship model is an originally designed one for the subject ship, whose wing section is MAU. The captive model tests with propeller models of the subject propeller in this study were not conducted. Although we should remind influences by difference of the propeller blade shape to the hydrodynamic characteristics in the maneuverability, since it is known that the hydrodynamic interaction coefficient is affected by the propeller loading condition [12], conducted test conditions with the original propeller model can be sufficient to construct the models for including expected operation range of the subject propellers.

The hull resistance characteristics are given in Table 5 from the results of the resistance test. The wave making resistance constant (C_W) in Eq. (2) is given as 4th-order function of the Froude number as shown in Eq. (18). These coefficients are determined through the ITTC recommended procedures [5].

Table 5. Coefficients of the model of the hull resistance in calm sea.

k	ΔC_F	c_{W0}	c_{W1}	c_{W2}	c_{W3}	c_{W4}
0.1332	2.884E-4	38.96	-18.95	3.646	-0.3116	9.97E-3

$$C_W = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=0}^4 c_{Wi} F_n^i, & \text{where } F_n > 0.1 \\ 0, & \text{where } F_n \leq 0.1 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Measured hull force and moment in the oblique towing test and the circular motion test are shown in Figure 3, with curves calculated by the hull model in Eq. (3) with coefficients given in Table 6. These coefficients are determined by the least square method, using the measured results. In the shown results of X_H , the hull resistance force was subtracted.

Figure 3. Measured results of the hull force and moment from the oblique towing test and the circulation motion test, and calculated results by determined coefficients. (“Exp” shows the measured results, “fitted” shows calculated results)

Table 6. Hydrodynamic coefficients in the hull model (Eq. (3)) of the subject ship.

X_{vv}	$X_{vr} + m_y'$	X_{rr}	X_{vvv}		
5.079E-03	0.2402	9.935E-03	0.5790		
Y_v	$Y_r - m_x'$	Y_{vv}	Y_{vr}	Y_{vr}	Y_{rr}
-0.3341	0.05531	-1.775	-0.1419	-0.4558	0.04619
N_v	N_r	N_{vv}	N_{vr}	N_{vr}	N_{rr}
-0.1762	-0.05834	0.05392	-0.2960	0.08815	-0.01166

The constants for the propeller model and the rudder model, shown in Eqs. (4), (7) and (16), are shown in Table 7. Self-propulsion test was conducted to determine the self-propulsion factor (w_P , t_P and η_R). The propeller effective wake fraction (w_P) is converted in the full-scale from the result of the self-propulsion test, using the ITTC recommended procedure [14]. The gradient coefficient of the rudder normal force (C_{N0}) is determined by the rudder open test. The η can be approximately given as ratio of the propeller diameter to the rudder height. The rudder effective wake fraction (w_R) is set by converting the w_R in the model-scale, which is determined from the results of the rudder force test in straightly advancing situation without the propeller model, using ratio of the w_P in the full-scale to in the model-scale.

Table 7. Constants of the propeller model and the rudder model for the subject ship.

Propeller	w_P	t_P	η_R		
	0.2330	0.1288	1.048		
Rudder	C_{N0}	η	δ_0	w_R	ε
	2.909	0.7889	0.0	0.3417	0.8583

The interaction coefficients of the rudder model (t_R , a_H , x_H) are analyzed by the rudder force test in straightly advancing situation, for measuring trends of the hull force and rudder normal force. Taken method to analyze the coefficient is as proposed as the MMG standard procedure [4]. Those tests were conducted in various combinations of the towing speed and the propeller rotational speed. The increment ratio of the propeller slipstream (k_x) is calculated by Eq. (7), using the analyzed rudder effective inflow velocity (u_R) by the MMG standard procedure [4] and the rudder effective wake fraction (w_R) by the rudder force test in straightly advancing situation without the propeller model. Analyzed coefficients are shown in Figure 4, with two horizontal axes of the constant representing the propeller loading condition. The one is the propeller advance constant (J) and the apparent propeller loading factor (τ) which is calculated by the propeller thrust as $\tau = 8T_P/\rho\pi D^2 u^2$, where T_P denotes the propeller thrust given in $T_P = \rho n_p^2 D^4 K_T$. The blue-colored point is the result at the service speed with the ship-point propeller rotation. We can confirm smooth trends of the analyzed value to each constant. These coefficient trends according to the J can be often seen in previous research as in [13].

Figure 4. Analyzed results of the rudder interaction coefficients and the increment ratio of propeller slipstream. (horizontal axis: lefthand side - the propeller advance constant, righthand side – the apparent propeller loading factor)

Considering these trends to the propeller loading condition, it is better to formulate these coefficients as a function with the variable representing the propeller loading condition, for comparing the difference of the maneuverability by two subject propellers. Authors regarded the τ as the proper variable for making approximation functions of these coefficients. Because the actually referred propeller loading condition is basically different in the two propellers at the same J . The approximated functions are given as shown in the dashed line on the results

with the axis of the τ . The coefficients of the polynomial formula are given in Table 8. It shall be noted that the determined function of the t_R was set not to calculate minus value, although some experimental values are minus. Because the range of the t_R is usually as from 0 to 0.2. Furthermore, the red-colored point in the results of the k_x was removed in determining the coefficients. Because that value was too low and outlier, where that value is known as at around 0.6. As one cause, authors consider the effect of the propeller slipstream was very weak due to the test condition where the set rotational speed was relatively lower to the towing velocity, as in $n_p = 6.0$ rps and the towing velocity is 1.084 m/s (service speed)

Table 8. Coefficients of the fitted polynomial formula ($y = \sum_{i=0} c_i \tau^i$) of the t_R , a_H , x_H and k_x .

	c_0	c_1	c_2	c_3
t_R	0.2795	-0.1645	0.03698	-3.029E-03
a_H	0.3657	-0.03144	3.622E-03	-1.546E-04
x_H/L	-0.3921	0.01011		
k_x	0.7101	-0.02692	1.107E-03	

As the hydrodynamic characteristics on the propeller and the rudder induced by transverse inflow direction at those position, the analyzed results of the influence function $f(v_P')$ shown in Eq. (5) and the rudder effective inflow velocity in transverse direction (v_R') are shown in Figure 5. These results are analyzed from measured data by the rudder force test in the oblique motion or the circular motion. The taken analysis method is proposed as the MMG standard procedure [4]. The gradients of the straight line in the v_R' are respectively corresponded to the flow straightening coefficient (γ_R) in each direction. We can confirm the trends are not symmetrical in the inflow direction.

Figure 5. Analyzed results of the influence function $f(v_P')$ for the propeller effective wake coefficient and the rudder effective inflow velocity in transverse direction (v_R').

The determined coefficients of the $f(v_P')$ and the flow straightening coefficients are shown in Table 9, given as according to the inflow direction.

Table 9. Coefficients of the function $f(v_P')$ as in ($f = 1 + \sum_{i=1} c_i v_P'^i$) and the flow straightening coefficients.

Inflow direction	c_1	c_2	c_3	γ_R	l_R/L
rightward	-1.587	6.079	-5.386	0.4355	-0.4594
leftward	-0.9733	4.575E-03	1.267	0.3411	-0.3357

3.2. The subject engine and parameters for the models of engine dynamics

For the subject ship of the Panamax-size bulk carrier shown in the last section, one actual main diesel engine is selected as a subject engine. Output and rotational speed of the subject engine at the MCR condition are 9065 kW and 88 RPM, referring the assessed results on the required power in the 90% MCR condition at the service speed. The recommended procedure by the ITTC performance committee [14] was applied to predict the required power from the result of the self-propulsion test. The type of the subject engine is two stroke, and cylinder number is six. The basic specs are shown in Table 10. The constants of the mechanical governor model are shown in Table 11. These constants are usually tuned through the results of shop trial tests or sea trials. In this study, since the

subject ship is not actually built, authors set these constants to make engine operations stable through the numerical speed trial in waves. The propeller is designed to be directly connected to the main engine without a gear system. Then, the engine rotational speed (n_e) is equaled to the propeller rotational speed (n_p).

Table 10. Basic specs of the subject engine for the subject ship.

Output (MCR) [kW]	n_e (MCR) [rps]	Q_e (MCR) [Nm]	z_C	V_C [m ³]	$I_e + I_m$ [kgm ²]
9065	1.467	9.837E+05	6	0.492	5.870E+04

Table 11. Constants of the mechanical governor model of the subject engine.

K_{SU}	K_S	K_i	$K_{i,b}$	K_{AW}	T_S [s]	T_i [s]	$\varepsilon_{D,B}$
1.180	2.0	0.4	0.001	10.0	0.5	4.8	5.0E-04

For constructing the C-CMV model which consists of multiple formulae, a lot of data and information are required. In this study, using the basic specs, results of the shop trial test, results of the sea trial test and the general technical data opened by one engine design company, the model coefficients are identified by the Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm [15], regarding this problem as optimization of multidimension complex function. As characteristics of the engine model shown in section 2.2, the limit line of the torque limiter function ($h_{P(Lim)}$) and the set function of the combustion efficiency constant (η_C) are shown in Figure 6. The combustion efficiency constant is set as a function of the relative ratio of the air mass flow to the fuel mass flow, whose standard value (λ_{af0}) is 2.1. The formulae of the is given in Eq. (19).

Figure 6. The set functions of the limit line of the torque limiter function ($h_{P(Lim)}$) in the nondimensional form and the combustion efficiency constant (η_C).

$$\overline{h_{p(Lim)}} = \begin{cases} 1.064\overline{n_e}, & \text{for } \overline{n_e} \leq 0.94 \\ 1.0, & \text{for } 0.94 < \overline{n_e} \leq 1.0 \\ 1.0/\overline{n_e}, & \text{for } 1.0 < \overline{n_e} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

3.3. Calculation conditions

Simulations of the turning test and the zigzag test are performed with the models and these coefficients shown as above. Set initial velocity before the rudder steers is 14.5 kt (7.49 m/s). The set rotational speed for the governor (n_{sp}) is determined through the speed trial test in numerical simulation. The set rotational speeds for each propeller are respectively 1.345 rps (91.7% of the MCR value) for the CFRP propeller and 1.346 rps (91.8% of the MCR value) for the metallic propeller. Though both values are almost equaled, the value of the metallic propeller is slightly higher. This is because the fitted results of the POC of the CFRP propeller shown in Figure 2 gives slightly higher value at that velocity.

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Time-series results and maneuverability indices

As examples of the simulated maneuvering motion, trajectories and time-series in the turning test for starboard side direction and time-series in the zigzag test whose starting rudder angle is -20 degree are shown in Figure 7

Figure 7. Simulated trajectories and time-series of the maneuvering motion in the turning test for starboard side direction.

Figure 8. Simulated time-series of the maneuvering motion in the zigzag test with set condition of -20/-20 degrees.

and Figure 8. The results by the metallic propeller are shown in blue-colored (in figure or table, “Metal”) and the results by the CFRP propeller are shown in red-colored (in figure or table, “CFRP”). In Figure 7, shown elapsed

time is until the ship's heading angle reaches 540 degrees. The items relating to the engine dynamics (n_p , Q_p , h_p) are given in nondimensional form by those value in the MCR condition, and the limit value by the torque limiter function ($h_{p(Lim)}$) is shown as dashed line in the figure of the fuel pump rack amount. The analyzed maneuverability indices of the turning test (Advance, Transfer and Tactical diameter) and the overshoot angles from the zigzag test are respectively shown in Table 12 and Table 13. For comparing with the conventional simulation without the engine models, analyzed values from the simulated result with fixed propeller rotational speed are also shown in parentheses.

Table 12. The analyzed maneuverability indices of the turning test.

δ [deg]	Propeller Type	Advance / L	Transfer / L	Tactical Dia. / L
+35	Metal	3.702 (3.697)	1.787 (1.786)	3.951 (3.920)
	CFRP	3.710 (3.706)	1.793 (1.791)	3.943 (3.935)
-35	Metal	3.873 (3.876)	1.856 (1.855)	4.002 (3.992)
	CFRP	3.869 (3.871)	1.856 (1.854)	4.001 (3.999)

Table 13. The analyzed overshoot angles of the zigzag test.

δ [deg]	Propeller Type	1st Overshoot angle [deg]	2nd Overshoot angle [deg]
+10/10	Metal	7.81 (7.83)	25.28 (25.15)
	CFRP	7.84 (7.85)	25.30 (25.16)
-10/-10	Metal	10.60 (10.53)	16.95 (16.94)
	CFRP	10.59 (10.54)	17.05 (17.26)
+20/20	Metal	15.70 (15.72)	24.25 (24.13)
	CFRP	15.78 (15.78)	24.40 (24.31)
-20/-20	Metal	20.20 (20.04)	18.57 (18.24)
	CFRP	20.21 (20.05)	18.43 (18.44)

From Figure 7 and Figure 8, we can confirm behaviors of the propeller thrust and the propeller torque in both propellers are different. These are because the propeller rotational speed behaves in different according to the loading condition on the main engine. As clearly shown in the h_p in Figure 7, it shall be pointed that the propeller rotational speed is significantly dropped when the torque limiter function saturates the fuel pump rack amount (as with an expedient description, when the solid line overlaps the dashed line) and the CFRP propeller can give higher rotational speed. This is because the CFRP propeller can keep the rotational speed higher than the metallic propeller and make the saturation effect by the torque limiter function less, due to lower torque constant in much loaded situation as shown in the POC in Figure 2. However, it seems that there are not much differences of the maneuvering motion between both propellers, especially for the result of the zigzag test.

Quantitatively comparing scores in Table 12 and Table 13, there are not significant differences between both propellers. Furthermore, there seems to be not quantitative and even qualitative difference on the inclusion of the engine model. Although most scores of the CFRP propeller are very slightly worse, it can be concluded that the difference of the maneuverability indices by the propeller characteristics or the inclusion of the engine dynamics are not significant.

4.2. Steady turning performance

For deeply assessing the effects by the CFRP propeller with the engine characteristics, the steady turning performance are analyzed as given in Figure 9. The surge velocity and the propeller thrust are given in relative form by the values from the speed trail test with the same set rotational speed, as represented as the u_0 and the T_{P0} .

The dashed lines in the figures of the engine rotational speed and the fuel pump rack amount respectively represent the set rotational speed to the governor (n_{sp}) and the limit value of the torque limiter function ($h_{p(Lim)}$).

Figure 9. Steady turning performance by the simulated result of the turning test with the engine models.

Firstly, it is noticeable that the results of the drift angle (β) and the yaw-rate in nondimensional form (r') in both propellers are equal as it happens. However, since the surge velocity by the CFRP propeller is higher, the physical values of the sway velocity and the yaw-rate by the CFRP propeller are actually larger than those by the metallic propeller. Therefore, the steady turning performance by the CFRP propeller is qualitatively better than that by the metallic propeller. Though a direct factor for this better performance is a higher propeller thrust of the CFRP propeller, the higher thrust is given by the higher propeller rotational speed, and that difference of the propeller rotational speed is induced by the difference of the fuel pump rack amount, as confirmed in Figure 9. As described in the last sub-section, since the torque coefficient of the metallic propeller is higher in low J region, the torque limiter function gave the metallic propeller further restriction of the fuel pump rack amount, whose restriction is more in the lower rotational speed as shown in Figure 6. Then, it can be concluded that the feature of the CFRP propeller which enables the main engine to operate in higher rotational speed extends the ship's steady turning performance.

5. Conclusions

For assessing the maneuverability of the ship equipped with the CFRP propeller, which is one of promising devices for improving the ship's propulsion performance, the simulations of the turning test and the zigzag test are performed. The simulation model consists of the MMG model, which represents the ship's hydrodynamic characteristics in maneuvering motion and the engine model based on the Combined CMV model. The subject ship is the Panamax-size bulk carrier equipped with the two-stroke main diesel engine. The subject propellers are the CFRP propeller designed for the subject ship and the conventional metallic propeller which gives the equivalent

propulsion performance at the service speed. From the simulated results, the CFRP propeller did not show the significant difference of the maneuverability indices of the turning test and the zigzag test (the advance, the transfer, the tactical diameter and the overshoot angles) compared to those by the metallic propeller. On the other hand, the CFRP propeller is expected to qualitatively improve the steady turning performance due to its preferable feature for the main engine, which enables it to operate at higher rotational speed and reduces the limiting effect of the torque limiter function of the governor.

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